

DARE to wear: digital health promotion and disease prevention using wearable devices

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Abstract

Global healthcare systems are under increasing strain to ensure long-term sustainability, necessitating a fundamental transition towards proactive, preventive healthcare strategies. Wearable sensor technologies are uniquely positioned to facilitate this paradigm shift by enabling continuous physiological and behavioral monitoring, facilitating early risk stratification, and enabling timely interventions. Digital lifelong prevention (DARE) is a nationwide initiative conceived in Italy to develop and evaluate novel digital tools and services aimed at fostering innovative health promotion and disease prevention pathways, with wearable devices identified as a critical enabling technology. Herein, we present a comprehensive overview of 16 pilot investigations designed in DARE to rigorously assess the utility of wearable devices in the continuous monitoring of physical activity, joint mobility, sleep architecture, heart rate variability, nutrition, and glucose homeostasis across diverse health domains, including healthy aging, chronic disease prevention, and lifestyle modification programs targeting over 20000 participants. We meticulously detail the methodological characteristics of these study protocols, explicitly outlining the technical specifications, functional capabilities, and inherent limitations of the 18 distinct wearable devices (sourced from 12 different manufacturers) employed across these clinical trials. The breadth of applications and the heterogeneity of the target populations underscore the significant potential of wearable devices as an integral component of future digital health prevention strategies.

1 Introduction

2 The global demographic landscape is undergoing a significant transformation
3 characterized by an unprecedented increase in the elderly population, primarily driven
4 by extended life expectancies and declining birth rates¹. This escalating aging trend
5 places substantial strain on healthcare systems worldwide, leading to heightened
6 demands for reactive responses, including hospital resources, long-term care facilities,
7 and healthcare professionals. Concomitantly, this demographic shift is associated with
8 a growing prevalence of chronic diseases², such as cardiovascular disorders³, cancers,
9 diabetes⁴, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and neurodegenerative conditions,
10 encompassing dementia⁵. The increasing burden of these long-term chronic conditions
11 necessitates more complex healthcare interventions and incurs significantly elevated
12 costs.

13 In this context, proactive prevention strategies are paramount, not only for improving
14 individual longevity and quality of life but also for mitigating the escalating financial
15 pressures on healthcare systems⁶. Prioritizing prevention through initiatives promoting
16 healthy aging, such as regular physical activity and balanced nutrition, can also
17 contribute to reducing health disparities. The impact of these initiatives can be amplified
18 by the integration of digital technologies, such as wearable devices and mobile health
19 apps, which offer the potential for broader and more accessible preventive care.

20 Digital technologies are revolutionizing healthcare by enhancing data accessibility
21 through efficient collection, storage, and sophisticated analysis of extensive health-
22 related datasets, thereby enabling the identification of critical trends and patterns.
23 Remote physiological and behavioral monitoring⁷, facilitated by wearable and Internet
24 of Things (IoT) devices, can provide crucial information for timely early interventions.
25 Telemedicine platforms further expand healthcare access⁸ by offering virtual
26 consultations, a particularly valuable resource for individuals living in geographically
27 remote areas⁹. Moreover, advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and sophisticated
28 data analytics are enabling the realization of personalized medicine, allowing for the
29 development of treatment regimens tailored to individual health profiles, incorporating
30 medical history and genetic predispositions.

31 Within this evolving digital landscape, wearable devices have garnered considerable
32 attention in the healthcare domain¹⁰. Their compact and lightweight design facilitates
33 unobtrusive long-term wear, while the integration of multiple low-power, energy-
34 efficient sensors enables continuous physiological and behavioral monitoring¹¹. These
35 devices, encompassing smartwatches, fitness trackers, and specialized IoT-enabled
36 sensors, can track a diverse array of health-related metrics. Beyond their widespread
37 adoption as personal health and wellness trackers, wearable devices are increasingly
38 being utilized across various clinical domains¹². For instance, in cardiology, continuous
39 heart rate monitoring¹³ and arrhythmia detection¹⁴ via wearables hold significant
40 promise for improving cardiovascular disease prevention¹⁵. Wearables are also
41 employed to objectively assess physical activity levels^{16,17}, gait patterns¹⁸, and overall

42 mobility¹⁹, proving particularly beneficial in the management of chronic conditions such
43 as Parkinson's disease and post-stroke rehabilitation²⁰. Recent studies have
44 demonstrated the high user acceptability of wearable devices in real-world settings²¹,
45 underscoring their ease of use and comfort. Furthermore, comprehensive reviews have
46 indicated that continuous monitoring via wearables enhances patient outcomes²² by
47 facilitating early disease detection and supporting the delivery of personalized
48 healthcare interventions²³. The seamless integration of wearable technology into
49 standard healthcare protocols represents a substantial advancement in personalized
50 health management.

51 Wearable devices possess the potential to play a transformative role in digital
52 prevention by facilitating access to and engagement with preventive health pathways.
53 In the realm of primary prevention, the adoption of wearables to support well-being and
54 healthy lifestyles²⁴ has demonstrated improvements in adherence to health-promoting
55 behaviors and a reduction in sedentary behavior²⁵. In secondary and tertiary prevention,
56 continuous physiological monitoring through wearable devices can enable the early
57 detection of adverse events and contribute to preventing the exacerbation of chronic
58 conditions²⁶.

59 However, the landscape of commercially available wearable devices is markedly
60 heterogeneous, encompassing a broad spectrum of technologies and analytical
61 capabilities, which can present significant challenges to their effective utilization. While
62 some devices are specifically engineered for research or clinical applications, the
63 majority of consumer-grade health trackers are not intended for direct clinical use. For
64 instance, these devices often lack comprehensive access to raw sensor data or employ
65 proprietary, non-standardized metrics, thereby complicating their integration into
66 clinical workflows. Nevertheless, certain functionalities of these consumer devices, such
67 as heart rate measurement, can be potentially leveraged for specific clinical and health
68 promotion applications. Critical considerations for researchers and clinicians include the
69 specific technical properties of these devices, their inherent limitations, and their
70 intended primary purposes. Furthermore, the current lack of standardized validation
71 methodologies for wearable devices²⁷, both in terms of metrological accuracy and
72 performance against established gold standards, introduces significant confounding
73 factors in the selection of the most appropriate technology for clinical or research
74 studies. In addition, the lack of medical device certification for many wearable devices
75 raises significant ethical and legal issues regarding data reliability and regulatory
76 compliance, thereby hindering their adoption in clinical research due to restrictions
77 imposed by local ethics committees. This complex scenario considerably impedes the
78 widespread adoption of these powerful tools, limiting their systematic application within
79 the healthcare domain.

80 Having recognized these challenges, researchers have established several international
81 research initiatives to address the barriers to the effective adoption of wearable devices
82 in healthcare, sharing open-source pipelines and resources to facilitate data
83 standardization, processing, and analysis. Mobilise-D (<https://mobilise-d.eu/>), a notable
84 project funded by the European Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) 2 Joint Undertaking
85 has focused on the identification and rigorous validation of digital outcomes derived
86 from wearable sensors for a range of chronic diseases, including chronic obstructive
87 pulmonary disease and neurodegenerative disorders. Mobilise-D has provided crucial
88 guidelines for the standardization of data streams from wearable devices²⁸, developed
89 validated digital mobility outcomes for monitoring daily-life gait to improve patient
90 follow-up and personalized care²⁹⁻³¹, and introduced an open-access, device-agnostic
91 pipeline for gait data analysis. Complementary IMI-funded initiatives such as RADAR-

92 CNS and RADAR-AD (<https://www.radar-ad.org/>) have made significant progress in the
93 application of wearable devices for continuous monitoring of patients with neurological
94 and psychiatric conditions, including epilepsy, depression, multiple sclerosis, and
95 Alzheimer's disease. A valuable outcome of these efforts is RADAR-BASE
96 (<https://www.radar-base.org/>), an open-source platform designed for the management
97 of data from multiple wearable devices and mobile technologies. Further supporting this
98 landscape is the Open Wearables Initiative (<https://www.owear.org/>), which aims to
99 promote the effective use of high-quality sensor-generated health measurements in
100 clinical research by openly sharing algorithms and datasets. Additionally, the Digital
101 Medicine Society (DiME) offers a comprehensive suite of resources, including
102 frameworks for sensor data integration ([https://dimesociety.org/access-
103 resources/sensor-data-integrations/](https://dimesociety.org/access-resources/sensor-data-integrations/)), to facilitate the development and application of
104 digital measures in healthcare, fostering innovation and collaboration across the digital
105 medicine ecosystem.

106 Successful implementations of wearable device technology in healthcare settings have
107 demonstrated their potential to enhance healthcare delivery and improve patient
108 outcomes. Building upon these advancements, a more pronounced emphasis on
109 preventive strategies offers a promising avenue for integrating wearable devices into
110 proactive healthcare paradigms, enabling early risk detection and continuous health
111 monitoring to promote overall well-being.

112 In this paper, we present the strategic framework for the use of wearable devices within
113 the DigitAl lifelong pREvention (DARE) initiative (<https://www.fondazioneedare.it/en/>), a
114 national flagship program funded by the Italian Ministry for University and Research
115 (MUR) under the National Plan for Complementary Investments to the National Recovery
116 and Resilience Plan (PNC). DARE was established to develop a distributed and
117 collaborative ecosystem focused on digital health prevention, bringing together
118 academic institutions, research centers, healthcare providers, and industry
119 stakeholders. Its primary objective is to generate and consolidate multidisciplinary
120 knowledge and solutions, spanning technical, legal, ethical, and organizational
121 dimensions, to support a systemic transition from reactive, disease-oriented care to
122 proactive, lifelong prevention and community-based health approaches.

123 Here, we describe how DARE operationalizes this vision through the structured use of
124 wearable technologies in preventive health, outlining the study protocols,
125 methodological approaches, and implementation strategies adopted. We also detail the
126 technical characteristics, functional capabilities, and limitations of the diverse wearable
127 devices deployed across DARE-affiliated studies, together with the validated data
128 processing pipelines used to derive clinically meaningful outcomes from unsupervised,
129 real-world monitoring. By sharing these insights, this report aims to inform and guide
130 similar international initiatives, providing a replicable model to accelerate the adoption
131 of digital tools in preventive healthcare and public health systems globally.

132 **Methods**

133 **DARE Initiative Framework**

134 The DigitAl lifelong pREvention (DARE) initiative is a four-year project that commenced
135 in December 2022. DARE's overarching aim is the development and validation of
136 innovative digital solutions to enable and enhance preventive health pathways,
137 facilitating their integration into routine healthcare practices and broader health-
138 promoting actions to achieve tangible improvements in the accessibility and quality of

139 healthcare services for citizens and patients. The consortium comprises twenty-seven
140 Italian partners, including universities, hospitals, local health authorities, research and
141 competence centers, and private sector entities. A multidisciplinary team of researchers
142 with expertise spanning engineering, computer science, public health, medicine, social
143 and legal sciences, economics, and ethics is collaboratively advancing the application
144 of digital tools and solutions in primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention areas.

145 DARE adopted a *bottom-up*, collaborative approach. Initially, participating partners,
146 leveraging their specific expertise, proposed digital-based assessment and monitoring
147 protocols to evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of preventive interventions across
148 diverse domains. Subsequently, partners with advanced capabilities in those areas
149 provided (and continue to provide) crucial technical and ethical-legal guidance on the
150 selection and implementation of the most appropriate digital technologies for these
151 studies.

152 This process has resulted in the proposition of 73 distinct research endeavors, referred
153 to within the DARE framework as “pilot studies”, designed to prospectively and
154 retrospectively collect and analyze relevant data from over two million citizens across
155 various areas of prevention (as illustrated in **Figure 1**). These pilot studies encompass
156 a range of relatively independent research projects focused on digital prevention
157 strategies.

158 As far as it is relevant for this article, wearable devices have emerged as a technology
159 of significant interest within the DARE initiative. A rigorous selection process was hence
160 implemented to ensure their appropriate application in each pilot study. Notably,
161 thirteen (18%) DARE pilot studies incorporate at least one wearable device to achieve
162 their specific research objectives. Furthermore, two externally funded satellite studies,
163 linked to specific DARE pilots but involving a distinct subset of healthy participants, and
164 one feasibility study within the DARE framework also utilize wearable devices.

Figure 1. Prevention areas addressed by DARE. The figure illustrates the various prevention areas investigated within the DARE initiative. Pilot studies employing wearable devices are indicated explicitly with a blue outline in their respective area(s) of focus. Note that individual pilot studies may address multiple prevention areas at a time.

165 Wearable Device Selection Methodology

166 The selection of wearable sensors for each pilot study commenced with specific requests
167 from the proposing partners. This involved a detailed articulation of the intended
168 context of device utilization, including the specific setting (e.g., laboratory-based
169 assessment versus ambulatory, free-living monitoring), the relevant health domain
170 (e.g., cardiology, oncology, metabolic health, neurology, or rehabilitation), and the
171 primary monitoring objectives, such as the specific physiological parameters to be
172 measured and tracked. Proposing partners could also solicit guidance from technical
173 partners within the DARE consortium to facilitate the selection process. The different
174 phases of the selection process were inspired by principles from the World Health
175 Organization's ExpandNet framework, which emphasizes the importance of planning
176 pilot projects with scaling up in mind. This approach encourages informed, strategic
177 decisions early in the design phase to enhance the potential for future scalability³².

178 A comprehensive technical evaluation was typically conducted to determine the
179 suitability of potential wearable devices. This evaluation rigorously assessed the
180 technical specifications of the devices, including their recording modalities,
181 measurement accuracy, battery longevity, physical burden (encumbrance), and
182 connectivity capabilities. Furthermore, the availability of robust evidence supporting the
183 quality of their measurements and the existence of publicly accessible processing
184 pipelines for effective data analysis were critical considerations. A key determinant in
185 the selection process was also the accessibility of raw data generated by the wearable
186 devices, as this is essential for enabling advanced post-processing analyses using
187 customized algorithms tailored to specific research questions. Recognizing that most
188 consumer-grade health trackers do not provide direct access to raw data, the potential
189 need for developing custom mobile or web applications to unlock this functionality was
190 also considered. Moreover, interoperability was a significant technical criterion,
191 ensuring that selected devices could address multiple research needs while seamlessly
192 integrating with existing data pre-processing and data analysis frameworks, which
193 typically require *raw* data as input. Potential constraints were also systematically
194 addressed during this process, including relevant regulatory requirements for medical
195 device certification, organizational challenges such as workflow integration complexities
196 and training requirements for clinical and research personnel, and financial
197 considerations encompassing the cost of device acquisition and ongoing maintenance.

198 Finally, candidate devices were carefully screened and recommended with the aim of
199 maximizing harmonization across different DARE pilot studies. This strategic approach
200 facilitates cross-study comparisons and enables comprehensive analyses across diverse
201 participant populations and health domains. This multi-faceted selection process
202 (depicted in **Figure 2**) ensures that each selected wearable sensor achieves an optimal
203 balance between specific research needs, inherent technical capabilities, adherence to
204 regulatory standards, and practical implementation constraints within the intended
205 prevention context defined by each pilot study.

Figure 2. Workflow for a wearable selection for each DARE pilot study. The workflow includes a comprehensive technical evaluation, the assessment of the ethical and practical constraints, and the harmonization of pilot studies protocols.

206 Results

207 DARE Pilot Studies Utilizing Wearable Devices

208 The DARE framework encompasses a diverse portfolio of pilot studies leveraging
 209 wearable technology for digital health promotion and disease prevention (**Figure 3**). Of
 210 the thirteen pilot studies incorporating wearable devices, the majority (n=9, 69%) are
 211 focused on primary prevention strategies, aiming to mitigate the onset of diseases or
 212 health issues by addressing modifiable risk factors. The remaining studies (n=4, 31%)
 213 target secondary or tertiary prevention, focusing on early detection of health issues or
 214 management of chronic conditions, respectively. These studies explore a range of
 215 applications for wearable devices, with a significant emphasis on monitoring physical
 216 activity (n=11, 85%), sleep patterns (n=6, 46%), heart rate (n=6, 46%), and, in one
 217 instance, glucose levels (n=1, 8%). A substantial proportion of these studies (n=11,
 218 85%) employ digital-based monitoring in unsupervised, real-world settings to capture
 219 ecologically valid data. A smaller subset (n=2, 15%) conducts data collection within
 220 controlled environments, such as hospitals or schools.

221 The defined pilot studies span several critical domains in the field of prevention. In the
 222 realm of learning and development, two studies (15%) are dedicated to identifying early
 223 markers of developmental disorders or tracking cognitive progression in pediatric and
 224 adolescent populations. A clinical trial is actively monitoring glucose levels in children
 225 with type 1 diabetes using continuous glucose monitoring systems. An orthopedics-
 226 focused study is evaluating physical function, gait characteristics, and balance in
 227 patients with musculoskeletal disorders, integrating in-laboratory assessments and
 228 wearable devices. Studies related to lifestyle and healthy aging (n=3, 23%) are
 229 investigating the influence of factors such as sleep and physical activity on overall well-
 230 being, as well as chronic disease prevention and management. Two studies (15%) are
 231 situated within the nutrition field: one focuses on the objective monitoring of food intake

232 in healthy individuals, while the other aims to elucidate the impact of specific nutritional
 233 interventions on the progression toward end-stage renal disease. In the context of
 234 neurological diseases, a clinical trial employs wearable devices to longitudinally monitor
 235 individuals with Down syndrome, with the objective of developing multimodal markers
 236 predictive of Alzheimer’s disease-related dementia onset and progression. Another
 237 clinical trial focuses on patients with sleep disorders to gain a deeper understanding of
 238 the intricate relationship between sleep quality and the development of frailty and
 239 mobility limitations. Finally, two studies (15%) centered on fall prevention are
 240 monitoring real-life gait mobility patterns in conjunction with sleep and HR data to
 241 assess fall risk in aging populations.

Figure 3. Overview of the DARE pilot studies across the life course, categorized by age group, type of prevention, setting, domain, and monitoring focus. Pilot studies are organized along three age bands: children and adolescents (<18 years), adults (18–65 years), and older adults (65+ years).

242 As detailed in **Table 1**, the DARE pilot studies encompass a broad spectrum of
 243 participant demographics, ranging from children with specific developmental (e.g.,
 244 Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder) or metabolic (e.g., Type-1 diabetes) conditions
 245 to healthy adults and frail older adults with elevated risk of falls and cognitive decline
 246 (e.g., due to Alzheimer’s disease). The planned sample sizes vary considerably across
 247 the DARE pilot studies, reflecting diverse research objectives. Some studies involve
 248 small, targeted cohorts to assess feasibility or gather preliminary insights, while others
 249 aim to identify lifestyle patterns and risk factors within larger population samples. The
 250 majority of the pilot studies included in the DARE framework are observational, aiming
 251 to investigate behavioral patterns with a focus on prevention and risk assessment.

252 The selection of wearable devices was meticulously aligned with the specific aims of
 253 each pilot study. Several studies utilize commercially available smartwatches. For
 254 instance, the Polar Ignite 3 (Polar Electro, Kempele, Finland) and Fitbit Inspire 3 (Fitbit
 255 Inc., San Francisco, USA) are employed for monitoring physical activity and HR in

256 pediatric populations, while the Garmin Fenix series (Garmin, Schaffhausen,
257 Switzerland) facilitates continuous activity tracking in adult cohorts. Conversely,
258 research-grade medical devices, such as the Empatica EmbracePlus (Empatica, Milan,
259 Italy), have been selected for advanced HR and sleep analyses requiring access to raw
260 physiological data. In pilot studies focusing on older adults, devices like the Activinsights
261 GENEActiv (Activinsights Ltd., Kimbolton, UK) and McRoberts Dynaport7 (McRoberts
262 B.V., The Hague, The Netherlands) have been chosen for their validated capabilities in
263 monitoring mobility and assessing fall risk.

264 The majority of the pilot studies (n=11, 85%) are conducted in real-world settings,
265 enhancing the ecological validity of the findings, as opposed to controlled environments
266 (n=2, 15%). The duration of data collection in these real-world settings exhibits
267 considerable variability, ranging from a minimum of 5 days to several months. A
268 significant proportion of studies (n=9, 69%) incorporate multiple assessment time
269 points (e.g., baseline and follow-up measurements at 6- to 12-month intervals), enabling
270 longitudinal analyses to track changes over time and identify potential temporal
271 patterns in the collected data. Most studies (n=12, 92%) integrate self-report
272 assessment tools, such as food and falls diaries and lifestyle questionnaires, to
273 complement the objective data streams obtained from wearable devices. Some pilot
274 studies are leveraging mobile applications (e.g., m-Path³³) to administer short
275 questionnaires at multiple time points throughout the day, thereby minimizing the
276 burden associated with traditional paper-based assessments.

277 The overarching objectives of the DARE pilot studies are multifaceted. In studies
278 involving children and adolescents, wearable devices are employed to detect early
279 markers associated with developmental disorders (*DARE-EMERALD*, *DARE-Child-*
280 *VISUO/SOCIAL*) or to develop an integrated mobile platform aimed at improving disease
281 management and reducing the risk of complications in Type-1 diabetes (TWIN). In
282 school-aged and adult populations, wearables are utilized to continuously monitor real-
283 life physical activity, sleep, and physiological parameters to develop predictive models
284 for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) (*DARE-Lifestyle*, *DARE-T21*) or to identify early
285 markers of mental health challenges associated with work-related stress, problematic
286 lifestyle behaviors, and dysfunctional work-life interfaces (*DARE-WORKLIFE*). The
287 *MAMBO* study aims to comprehensively assess biomechanical and postural alterations
288 in adults with multiple osteochondromas using wearable devices within controlled
289 laboratory settings. *DARE-ADPKD* and *FitMate* are employing wrist-worn devices to
290 monitor food intake in individuals with Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease
291 (ADPKD) and healthy adults, respectively. In elderly populations, the primary focus is on
292 fall risk assessment (*DARE-FALLSPREDICT*, *DARE-POWERAGEING*) and on elucidating the
293 complex relationship between sleep disturbances and the onset or progression of
294 cognitive impairment, frailty, or sarcopenia (*SOMNUS-DARE*, *CAN-DARE*).

295 Despite the inherent heterogeneity of the individual pilot studies, concerted efforts have
296 been made to standardize methodologies and ensure comparability across different
297 investigations, fostering potential synergies in data processing and subsequent
298 analyses. An analysis of the sensor placement strategies across the thirteen studies
299 revealed that 4 (31%) utilize a single inertial measurement unit positioned on the lower
300 back, 6 (46%) employ wrist-worn sensors to capture mobility and physiological
301 parameters, and 3 (23%) utilize a combination of both sensor locations.

302 **DARE Feasibility Study Utilizing Wearable Devices**

303 A dedicated feasibility study within the DARE framework (*GARMIN feasibility*) has been
304 defined to evaluate the practical implementation of a web portal designed for Garmin
305 smartwatches to facilitate remote monitoring of the general population in real-life
306 scenarios. Physiological parameters and motion data of interest are collected from a
307 cohort of twenty healthy young adults, and their daily physical activity patterns are
308 analyzed. To achieve this, each participant was equipped with a Garmin smartwatch
309 over an extended period of 2 years, and to enhance the robustness of the experimental
310 evaluation, various Garmin wearable models were included in the study protocol.

311 **DARE Satellite Pilot Studies Utilizing Wearable Devices**

312 Two satellite pilot studies were specifically designed to complement the main *DARE-*
313 *FALLSPREDICT* pilot study and to address nuanced aspects of mobility and monitoring
314 in distinct populations and settings. The LOOKING-GLASS MIAR study investigated the
315 feasibility of employing a sparse network of wearable devices to estimate the kinematics
316 and HR correlates of simple motor tasks that may elevate fall risk, such as picking up
317 objects from the floor, while also capturing nighttime sleep data. This study was
318 conducted on twelve healthy young adults during in-lab assessments utilizing state-of-
319 the-art stereophotogrammetry and incorporated single-night real-life sleep monitoring.
320 In contrast, the LOOKING-GLASS DR study is a pilot investigation designed to monitor
321 physical activity, sleep patterns, and HR in a cohort of 24 older adults with a
322 documented history of falls during a 5-day hospitalization period, aiming to explore the
323 feasibility and utility of wearable device deployment for fall prevention in geriatric
324 inpatients.

325 *Table 1. Overview of DARE pilot studies with wearables: population, wearable devices, data collection methods, and objectives.*

Study	Title	Population domain	Sample size	Wearables	Wearables domain	Time points with wearables	Setting	Diaries	Questionnaires	Objective
DARE-EMERALD	Early markers and correlates of learning disorders and ADHD	Children	300	Polar Ignite 3	Mobility	5 (M0,M6, M12,M12, M24)	Real life (1 day)	-	Attention, hyperactivity (task: learning, cognition)	To identify early markers and behavioral correlates of hyperactivity symptoms and associated learning difficulties
TWIN	A New Digital Twin-Based Clinical Decision Support System for Type 1 Diabetes Management in Children	Children with type 1 diabetes	80	Fitbit Inspire 3	Physical activity	1	Real life (6 months)	Food	Quality of life, system usability, glucose control	Develop a clinical decision support system to optimize the insulin therapy of children with type 1 diabetes under multiple daily injections
DARE-Child-VISUO/SOCIAL	A multidimensional and multimodal analysis of visuospatial and socio-relational abilities in typical and atypical development	Typical children and adolescents	150	Empatica EmbracePlus	HR	2	Clinical	-	Arousal, worries, perception of competence	To develop new digital measures and understand the role of cognitive and socio-relational skills in terms of primary prevention
MAMBO	Accessible measurements of mobility and deformity biomarkers for orthopedic treatments	Adults with Multiple osteochondromas	30	Euleria lab Ultium Motion	Mobility	2 (M0, M12)	Clinical	-	Quality of life, balance	Monitor the quality of life and increase the understanding of disease evolution; identify biomechanical and postural alterations supporting preventive treatments
DARE-Lifestyle	Monitoring lifestyles and health determinants in different settings and population targets	Children, adolescents, young adults, adults	20000	Fitbit Inspire 3	Sleep, HR, physical activity	2 (M0, M6)	Real life (7 days)	Food	Physical activity and sedentary behavior, diet and nutrition, sleep, dependencies (e.g., smoke, alcohol, drugs), migraine	To develop predictive models for identifying individuals at risk and planning interventions for the primary prevention of NCDs
DARE-WORKLIFE	Preventing psychological issues related to work and lifestyles in the digital transition era	General working population	100	Empatica EmbracePlus	Sleep, HR, physical activity	1	Real life (5 days)	Sleep, job demands, techno-stress,	Mental health, lifestyle, work characteristics, work-life balance	Monitor job demands, techno-stress, work-life balance, sleep, physical activity, and diurnal and nocturnal heart rate variability to identify

								work-life balance		early markers of mental health problems
DARE-ADPKD	Digital therapy and telemedicine approaches for nutritional intervention in Patients with Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD)	Patients with ADPKD	150	FitBit Sense 2	Wrist movement for food intake	1	Real life (12 months)	Food	-	To evaluate the impact of specific nutritional approaches on progression to end-stage renal disease in patients with ADPKD
FitMate	Food Intake Tracker and Metabolic Evaluation for Health Enhancement	Healthy Adults	1000	Fitbit Sense 2, Garmin Vivoactive 5, Garmin Fenix 7S	Wrist movements	5 (M0,M6, M12,M12, M24)	Real life (1 month)	Food	-	To estimate eating episodes, types of food, and caloric intake with commercial devices
DARE T21	Digital biomarkers in Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease and Down Syndrome -	Adults with Down Syndrome (T21)	60	Activinsights GENEActiv, Empatica EmbracePlus	Sleep, HR, physical activity	1	Real life (7 days)	-	-	To develop multimodal markers, based on the integration of innovative digital approaches, clinical and neuropsychological assessments, and molecular analyses, to predict the onset and progression of dementia due to AD in the population of adults with T21
SOMNUS-DARE	The role of sleep disorders in the motoric and cognitive trajectories of older physically frail sarcopenic and healthy active subjects	Physically frail older adults, Healthy, active older adults	300	McRoberts Dynaport 7, GENEActiv, Sleep Profiler	Sleep, mobility	3 (M0, M12, M24)	Real life (7 days)	Sleep, food	Cognition, physical activity, nutrition, quality of life, sleep, optimism	To gain a deeper understanding of the impact of sleep disorders on physical frailty, sarcopenia, mobility disability, and cognitive impairment
DARE-FALLSPRED ICT	Development of a state-of-the-art multi-variable model for fall risk estimation in frail elderly subjects and	Frail older adults, Older adults	1084	McRoberts Dynaport 7, Activinsights GENEActiv	Sleep, mobility	2 (M0, M6)	Real life (7 days)	Falls, sleep	-	Develop a model for fall risk estimation

	the general population	Older adults	200	McRoberts Dynaport 7, Empatica EmbracePlus	Sleep, HR, mobility	2 (M0, M6)	Real life (7 days)	Falls, sleep	-	
CAN-DARE	Clinical and neuropsychological markers of healthy ageing	Healthy older adults	100	Activinsights GENEActiv, Axivity AX6	Sleep, mobility	2 (M0, M6)	Real life (7 days)	-	-	Monitor sleep and mobility in healthy adults and adults with initial cognitive decline
DARE-POWERAGING	Analysis of loss of muscle strength and power and degradation of motor control over time as a tool for predicting falls in a population with knee osteoarthritis.	Older adults with osteoarthritis	50	McRoberts Dynaport 7	Mobility	5 (M0, M6, M12, M12, M24)	Real life (5 days)	Falls	-	Understand whether muscle power and muscle control degradation may be better predictors of falls compared to muscle force

Legend: AD - Alzheimer's disease; ADPKD - Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease; HR - Heart Rate; M - month; NCDs - Non Communicable Diseases; T21 - Trisomy 21.

326 **Current Status of DARE Pilot Studies Utilizing Wearable Devices**

327 As of August 1st, 2025, all the DARE pilot studies utilizing wearable devices have
 328 received approval from the relevant ethical committees, and participant recruitment
 329 has commenced for ten of these studies.

330 **Wearables in DARE Framework: Technical Specifications and Practical**
 331 **Applications**

332 Seventeen distinct wearable devices have been selected for integration across the pilot
 333 studies within the DARE framework (as shown in **Figure 3** and detailed in **Table 2**).
 334 These devices encompass a diverse range of functional domains, including the
 335 monitoring of physical activity (n=15, 83%), sleep (n=13, 72%), heart rate (n=11, 61%),
 336 and glucose levels (n=1, 6%). In the context of continuous, real-world physical activity
 337 monitoring, the predominant sensor placement is wrist-worn, with the notable
 338 exceptions of the McRoberts Dynaport sensor, which is positioned at the lower back
 339 using an elastic belt, and the Axivity AX6 sensor (Axivity Ltd, Leicester, UK), which offers
 340 flexible body attachment via medical tape. Battery life varies across devices and is
 341 influenced by selected data collection settings, such as sampling frequency. A
 342 substantial majority of the selected sensors (n=16, 89%) are waterproof according to
 343 established water resistance ratings (e.g., Ingress Protection or Atmospheres), ensuring
 344 their operational integrity across diverse environmental conditions and use cases.
 345 However, it is important to note that only six devices (33%) have received CE
 346 certification as medical devices (under the Medical Device Directive (MDD, 93/42/EEC)
 347 or in accordance with the European Union’s Medical Device Regulation (MDR)), and
 348 seven devices (39%) have obtained Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval.

349

Figure 3: Overview of wearable devices used in the DARE initiatives, categorized by monitoring domains, attachment site, battery life, water resistance, smartphone dependency, and medical certification status. The figure lists 17 wearable devices, distinguishing between research-grade (green outline) and commercial (blue outline) products. Legend: *water-resistant, but water rating is not specified in the device documentation.

350 The following section provides a detailed overview of each selected wearable device,
351 outlining key technical specifications, usability features, information regarding available
352 data streams (e.g., type, sampling frequency (*fs*), range), and associated tools (e.g.,
353 mobile applications, Software Development Kits (SDKs)).

354

355 1. *ActiveInsights GENEActiv*

356 The GENEActiv³⁴ is a waterproof Class-I medical device (under MDD 93/42/EEC; FDA
357 510(k) exemption) providing high-resolution tri-axial *raw* accelerometer data (up to 100
358 Hz, ± 16 g), ambient light exposure (up to 100 Hz, 0-3000 Lux), and skin temperature
359 (up to 100 Hz, 0-60°C). Its versatile design allows for placement on various body
360 locations (e.g., lower back, ankle) using medical tape or dedicated accessories (e.g.,
361 wrist band, adjustable elastic belt). An integrated event marker button enables users to
362 annotate specific events or activities directly within the data stream. Logging durations
363 can reach up to 30 days at a sampling frequency of 20 Hz and 7 days at 100 Hz. The
364 device achieves full charge within 3 hours using a dedicated charging cradle. Data can
365 be downloaded to a local computer via the provided free software in .csv or .bin format
366 and can be processed using custom analysis pipelines. Notably, the device can function
367 as a stand-alone data logger without requiring data transfer to the vendor's cloud or an
368 active Internet connection. The GENEActiv has been extensively utilized in scientific
369 literature, particularly in studies focusing on physical activity³⁵, sleep/wake patterns,
370 and circadian rhythms^{36,37}.

371 Within the DARE framework, the GENEActiv is employed in five distinct pilot studies
372 (*SOMNUS-DARE*, *DARE T21*, *DARE-EMERALD*, *DARE-FALLSPREDICT*, *LOOKING GLASS*
373 *DM*), always in conjunction with other wearable devices (i.e., EmbracePlus, DynaPort 7,
374 AX6) to monitor sleep and/or physical activity across a wide range of populations, from
375 pediatric to healthy or frail older adults.

376 2. *McRoberts DynaPort*

377 The DynaPort 7 is a Class-I medical device incorporating a tri-axial accelerometer
378 ($fs=100$ Hz, range ± 16 g), a tri-axial gyroscope ($fs = 100$ Hz, range ± 2000 degree per
379 second (dps)), a barometer ($fs = 1$ Hz, range 330-1100 hPa), and a temperature sensor
380 ($fs = 1$ Hz), rendering it suitable for assessing physical activity and mobility in real-world
381 settings. It is designed to be worn comfortably on the lower back using an elastic belt
382 and has demonstrated good acceptability among elderly users³⁸. The device is not
383 waterproof and requires removal before water-based activities. The updated version of
384 the DynaPort 7 firmware offers continuous measurement for approximately 8 days with
385 active accelerometers and gyroscopes sampling at 100 Hz. Data can be directly
386 downloaded to a PC (in .omx format) without mandatory cloud transfer, with an optional
387 upload to the McRoberts' cloud. Reading .omx files currently necessitates the use of
388 specific custom routines implemented in MATLAB (The Mathworks, Inc.), excluding
389 barometer data. McRoberts integrates the Mobilise-D algorithm³⁹⁻⁴¹ for computing
390 digital mobility outcomes within its analytics pipeline, which requires a software license.

391 The Dynaport 7 is utilized in four DARE pilot studies (*SOMNUS-DARE*, *DARE-*
392 *FALLSPREDICT*, *DARE-POWERAGING*, *LOOKING-GLASS DR*) for monitoring sleep and/or
393 activity patterns.

394 3. *Axivity AX6*

395 The AX6 is a waterproof data logger featuring a 6-axis motion sensor that measures
396 both acceleration (fs = 12.5-100 Hz, range $\pm 2/\pm 4/\pm 8/\pm 16g$) and angular velocity (fs =
397 12.5-100 Hz, range 125-2000 dps). Additionally, it captures light exposure (fs = 12.5-
398 100 Hz, range 3-1000 Lux) and skin temperature (fs = 12.5-100 Hz, range 0-40°C),
399 which can aid in detecting periods of non-wear. The integrated sensors offer
400 configurable sampling rates, enabling continuous long-term data collection (e.g., up to
401 7 days with fs = 100 Hz for both accelerometer and gyroscope; up to 34 days collecting
402 only acceleration sampled at 50 Hz). A soft-touch silicone band facilitates easy wrist
403 attachment, and the sensor can also be affixed to the body using medical adhesive
404 patches. Data can be directly downloaded to a PC (in .cwa or .csv format) via a USB
405 port using dedicated open-source software (AX3 GUI) and subsequently imported for
406 post-processing in various analysis environments (e.g., MATLAB, Python). Notably, *raw*
407 acceleration and angular velocity data acquired with Axivity sensors can be analyzed
408 using McRoberts' analytics, ensuring consistent analysis results in projects that employ
409 both sensor types⁴². Axivity sensors are frequently employed in research to differentiate
410 between individuals with and without a history of falls, as well as to monitor longitudinal
411 changes in activity patterns and fall risk among older adults^{43,44}, including in low-
412 resource settings⁴³. Furthermore, Axivity sensors have been utilized in sleep-focused
413 research^{45,46}.

414 The AX6 is employed in a single pilot study (*DARE-EMERALD*) to monitor sleep and
415 mobility in healthy adults with initial cognitive impairment and in one of the satellite
416 pilot studies (*LOOKING GLASS MIAR*) during in-laboratory motor tasks and sleep
417 monitoring.

418 4. *Empatica EmbracePlus*

419 The EmbracePlus is a wrist-worn wearable medical device (FDA-cleared, CE-certified as
420 a Class IIa medical device under the European Union's MDR) designed for continuous
421 physiological data monitoring in real-world settings. The device is lightweight and water-
422 resistant, promoting user comfort and adherence for 24/7 monitoring. It incorporates a
423 triaxial accelerometer (fs = 64 Hz, range $\pm 16g$), a tri-axial gyroscope (fs = 1-4 Hz, range
424 ± 2000 dps), a photoplethysmography (PPG) sensor (fs = 64 Hz), a skin temperature
425 sensor (fs = 1-4 Hz, range 0-50°C), and two sensors integrated into the strap for
426 measuring electrodermal activity (fs = 1-4 Hz, range 0.01-100 μS). The battery typically
427 lasts up to 48 hours, depending on usage and data transmission frequency. EmbracePlus
428 transmits real-time data to a paired compatible smartphone via the Bluetooth Low
429 Energy (BLE) protocol. In the absence of a smartphone connection (e.g., disconnection
430 or power off), the device can store up to 36 hours of data in its internal memory (the
431 amount of raw data recorded is dependent on the amount of activity performed and the
432 levels of heart rate recorded); beyond this period, data recording ceases until a
433 connection is re-established with the mobile application. Notably, on iOS devices, the
434 application automatically resumes operation upon smartphone restart, whereas Android
435 devices require manual re-opening of the application. Effective management of data
436 collection and a successful data export necessitate the use of compatible smartphones
437 due to the device's utilization of Bluetooth® 5.0 with 2M PHY, which imposes specific
438 compatibility constraints. Data are initially stored locally on the smartphone and
439 automatically uploaded to the Empatica cloud (USA-based, GDPR-compliant) upon
440 internet connectivity. While recordings can occur without Wi-Fi, an initial and final Wi-Fi
441 connection is required. Wi-Fi connectivity enables additional functionalities, such as
442 real-time monitoring of participants' compliance via the Empatica portal. While peer-
443 reviewed literature specifically on the EmbracePlus is currently limited^{47,48} due to its
444 recent market introduction, the preceding version (E4 wrist-band) has been extensively

445 validated across a wide range of applications, including physiological monitoring and
446 stress and pain assessment⁴⁹⁻⁵¹.

447 The EmbracePlus is utilized in four DARE pilot studies with diverse objectives: to assess
448 potential changes in HR in response to cognitive tasks in children (*DARE-Child-*
449 *VISUO/SOCIAL*); to monitor physiological responses to work-related stress and other
450 daily experiences as early biomarkers of mental health problems (*DARE-WORKLIFE*); as
451 a source of biomarkers for predicting dementia in adults with Trisomy 21 population
452 (*DARE-T21*); and to feed a model for fall risk estimation (*DARE-FALLSPREDICT*).

453 *5. Garmin Fenix 7S/7S Solar*

454 The Fenix 7S is a commercially available waterproof smartwatch equipped with a
455 comprehensive suite of integrated sensors, including PPG, accelerometer, gyroscope,
456 skin temperature sensor, barometer, altimeter, and GPS. It can also be paired with
457 external devices to monitor additional parameters such as blood pressure, body mass
458 index (BMI), HR, and running dynamics. To access data collected by the Garmin Fenix
459 7S, users must create a personal account on the Garmin Connect web portal and log
460 in through both the portal and the companion mobile application. The smartwatch must
461 then be paired with a compatible smartphone, enabling data synchronization via the
462 Bluetooth Low Energy protocol. Once paired, all collected data are automatically stored
463 within the Garmin Connect cloud systems upon synchronization, providing users with
464 centralized access for monitoring and management. Garmin also offers access to
465 collected data through a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) available via
466 the Garmin Connect Developer Program. To enable this functionality, users must provide
467 explicit consent for data access, thereby allowing seamless integration with third-party
468 platforms and applications.

469 The Fenix 7S is employed in the *FitMate* pilot study, to estimate eating episodes, and in
470 the feasibility study (*GARMIN feasibility*), to evaluate the use of commercial wearable
471 devices for monitoring daily activities.

472 *6. Garmin Forerunner 255*

473 The Forerunner 255 is a water resistant smartwatch, specifically designed for running
474 and triathlon activities, also including a variety of sport profiles, such as cycling, hiking
475 and strength training. It is equipped with a GPS sensor, a barometer, an altimeter, a
476 magnetometer, a gyroscope, an accelerometer, a thermometer, and a PPG. The battery
477 life is reported to last up 14 days under standard operating conditions; however, it is
478 significantly reduced in GPS mode, lasting approximately 30 hours. With its 5 ATM water
479 resistance rating, the device can be used confidently for swimming and aquatic sports,
480 whether in a pool or open water. As the Garmin Fenix 7s model, the Forerunner 255 is
481 compatible with external devices such as the Garmin Index™ BPM and the Garmin
482 Index™ S2 to monitor additional parameters such as the blood pressure and BMI. The
483 procedure to access Garmin collected data through the Garmin Connect portal is the
484 same described for the Garmin Fenix 7s model.

485 The Forerunner 255 is used in the feasibility study (*GARMIN feasibility*) to evaluate the
486 use of Garmin devices for monitoring daily activities.

487 *7. Garmin Instinct 2 Solar*

488 The Instinct 2 Solar is an ultra-resistant waterproof smartwatch, specifically designed
489 for outdoor activities. It is equipped with a GPS sensor, a barometer, an altimeter, a
490 magnetometer, a gyroscope, an accelerometer, a thermometer, and a PPG. The device

491 has an extended battery life of up to 28 days with solar charging, assuming continuous
492 daily wear and around three hours of exposure to outdoor light at 50000 lux. The
493 device's ATM water resistance allow for a broad spectrum of water-based activities,
494 including showering, swimming, diving, and snorkelling. The device is compatible with
495 external devices such as the Garmin Index™ BPM and the Garmin Index™ S2, and with
496 the Gamin Connect portal. The procedure to retrieve the collected data is the same
497 described for other Garmin smartwatch models.

498 The Forerunner 255 is employed in the feasibility study (*GARMIN feasibility*), to evaluate
499 the use of Garmin devices for monitoring daily activities.

500 8. *Garmin VivoActive 5*

501 The Vivoactive 5 is a water-resistant fitness smartwatch that provides activity tracking,
502 HR monitoring, and sleep and stress analysis. It is equipped with an accelerometer, a
503 PPG sensor, a thermometer, and GPS. For activity tracking, the device offers several
504 features, including step counting, estimation of calories burned, distance traveled, and
505 automatic detection of walking and running. With a 5 ATM water resistance rating, the
506 device is also suitable for water-based sports, including both pool and open-water
507 swimming. The battery life is reported to last up to 11 days in smartwatch mode and up
508 to 21 hours in GPS mode, supporting its use in long-duration outdoor exercise
509 monitoring. As with other Garmin devices, users can access their activity data via the
510 Garmin Connect mobile app or web-based platform, enabling the retrieval of insights
511 related to training, monitoring, and overall health trends. Several scientific studies have
512 investigated the reliability and acceptability of smartwatches from the Vivoactive
513 series^{52,53}.

514 The Vivoactive 5 is employed in the *FitMate* pilot study to monitor food intake through
515 wrist-based movement tracking.

516 9. *Fitbit Sense 2*

517 The Fitbit Sense 2 smartwatch is equipped with an accelerometer, a PPG sensor, and
518 ambient light sensors. It offers comprehensive sleep tracking, including detailed sleep
519 stage classification, and has the capability to detect instances of snoring. A built-in GPS
520 module allows users to monitor outdoor activities with a high degree of precision. The
521 device's battery life is reported to last up to 6 days on a single charge, depending on
522 usage. Fitbit provides a set of public Device and Web APIs that developers can use to
523 retrieve raw data collected by Fitbit trackers, as well as manually enter log data. For
524 research applications, the web-based platform Fitabase (<https://www.fitabase.com/>) is
525 widely adopted to monitor real-time trends and export aggregated data in .CSV format
526 (daily, hourly, and minute-level resolution) from individual participants. In the context
527 of the DARE pilot study (*DARE-ADPKD*), a dedicated web application was developed to
528 enable the acquisition and storage of *raw* data from Fitbit devices. The Fitbit Sense 2
529 has been employed in several research studies to monitor physical activity levels and
530 heart rate variability (HRV), particularly in populations with chronic health
531 conditions^{53,54}. However, it should be noted that sleep scoring by the Fitbit Sense shows
532 only moderate agreement with polysomnography, both in two-stage (wake/sleep) and
533 four-stage (wake, light sleep, deep non-rapid eye movement sleep, and rapid eye
534 movement sleep) classification, and is therefore best suited for studies involving
535 predominantly healthy sleepers⁵⁵.

536 The Fitbit Sense 2 is used in a single DARE pilot study (*DARE-ADPKD*) to evaluate
537 different nutritional approaches in patients with ADPKD.

538

10. Fitbit Inspire 3

539 The Fitbit Inspire 3 is a low-cost fitness tracker equipped with a PPG sensor, an
540 accelerometer, and an ambient light sensor. It supports the monitoring of physiological
541 parameters such as breathing rate, skin temperature, and HRV. The device features a
542 removable wristband and can alternatively be worn clipped to clothing; however, in this
543 configuration, certain functionalities (e.g., HR tracking) are disabled. As with the Fitbit
544 Sense 2, Fitbit provides developers with a comprehensive suite of public Device and
545 Web APIs, enabling access to raw user data for research and integration purposes. Fitbit
546 Inspire devices have been employed in various studies to monitor physical activity,
547 sleep, and HRV over extended periods^{56,57}.

548 The Fitbit Inspire 3 is used in two pilot trials. In the *TWIN* study, it provides data to a
549 decision support system for diabetes therapy optimization. In the *DARE-Lifestyle* pilot
550 study, it supports the development of predictive models for the early identification of
551 NCDs in young populations.

552

11. Polar Ignite 3

553 The Polar Ignite 3 is a fitness and wellness smartwatch designed to monitor sleep,
554 physical activity, and HR. It is equipped with a set of integrated sensors, including an
555 optical HR sensor, accelerometer, ambient light sensor, and skin temperature sensor.
556 The device also includes a GPS module for accurate outdoor activity tracking. The Ignite
557 3 provides several insights into sleep quality: (i) it tracks sleep stages; (ii) it integrates
558 sleep and autonomic nervous system data to generate a recovery score from stress and
559 training; and (iii) it provides a summary sleep quality score. However, published
560 validation data comparing its sleep metrics to gold-standard polysomnography are
561 currently limited⁵⁸. The battery life extends up to 30 hours in continuous training mode
562 with GPS and HR monitoring enabled. The device can be synchronized with *third-party*
563 fitness applications to share training data and is compatible with the Polar H10 chest
564 strap, which enhances HR measurement accuracy. Processed data are accessible
565 through the Polar Flow app and the Polar website on both Android and iOS platforms.
566 Access to *raw* data is available via the Polar Flow ecosystem for research applications.

567 The Polar Ignite 3 is used in a single study (*DARE-EMERALD*) aimed at identifying
568 potential early biomarkers in children presenting with hyperactivity symptoms and
569 learning difficulties.

570

12. Polar H10

571 The Polar H10 is a lightweight HR monitoring device designed for athletes. It utilizes
572 electrocardiogram (ECG) technology through electrodes embedded in an adjustable
573 chest strap, allowing for accurate HR recording⁵⁹. The strap includes non-slip silicone
574 inserts to enhance grip and prevent displacement during intense physical activity,
575 including water-based activities. The device features built-in memory, enabling
576 standalone data collection without requiring a connected smartphone or receiver. Its
577 battery lasts up to 400 hours, depending on usage, and can be replaced with a standard
578 CR2025 coin cell. Processed data can be accessed through the Polar Flow mobile app
579 and website, while *raw* data are available via the Polar SDK for both Android and iOS
580 platforms. The Polar H10 is widely used as a gold-standard reference in validation
581 studies of commercial wearable devices for HR monitoring^{60,61}

582 In the framework of DARE, it was employed in one of the satellite pilot studies (*LOOKING*
583 *GLASS MIAR*) to record HR data during in-lab motor tasks and sleep.

584

13. Polar Verity Sense

585 The Polar Verity Sense is an optical HR sensor designed to be worn on the upper arm
586 or forearm using an adjustable elastic armband. In addition to the PPG sensor, it
587 integrates an accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer to support multi-modal
588 physiological and movement tracking. The device offers three operational modes,
589 selectable via a button on the unit: (i) *swim mode*, for tracking metrics such as HR and
590 distance during swimming workouts (with IPX8 water resistance), using a clip that
591 attaches to swim goggles; (ii) *HR mode*, for continuous HR monitoring; and (iii) *recording*
592 *mode*, which stores data in internal memory for later analysis. The Verity Sense can be
593 paired with a smartwatch or mobile app to visualize workout data in real time or access
594 post-session summaries. The device has a battery life of up to 24 hours, depending on
595 the intensity and duration of use, and can be recharged via a micro-USB port. Processed
596 data are accessible through the Polar Flow mobile app and website, while *raw* data can
597 be retrieved via the Polar SDK, available for both Android and iOS platforms. The Polar
598 Verity Sense has demonstrated validity for 24-hour physical activity monitoring⁶².

599 The Polar Verity Sense was used in one of the satellite pilot trials (*LOOKING GLASS MIAR*)
600 to record HR and pulse wave data during in-lab motor tasks and sleep, in combination
601 with the Polar H10.

602

14. Rooti Rx

603 Rooti Rx is a portable ECG medical device classified as Class IIa under the European
604 Medical Device Regulation (MDR). It is designed for continuous HR monitoring for up to
605 seven consecutive days. The device is applied to the upper chest using an adhesive
606 patch and electrodes, enabling ECG-based HR recording. Its compact and lightweight
607 form factor allows it to be worn discreetly under clothing, in contrast to traditional Holter
608 monitors, which typically require multiple electrodes and external wiring. To ensure
609 high-quality signal acquisition, proper skin preparation - such as hair removal and
610 cleaning - is recommended prior to application. The device includes an event button
611 that users can press to mark specific occurrences (e.g., palpitations), facilitating
612 retrospective analysis by healthcare professionals. The Rooti Rx app (available
613 exclusively on iOS devices, including iPad) is required to initiate the recording and, upon
614 completion, to upload data to the vendor's GDPR-compliant cloud server located in
615 Ireland. Once recording has begun, the device is capable of storing up to 7 days of
616 continuous ECG data (sampling rate = 250 Hz) and tri-axial accelerometer data
617 (sampling rate = 31.25 Hz). Upon completion of the session, *raw* data are uploaded to
618 the cloud and can be subsequently downloaded for local analysis and review. Indexes
619 derived from chest acceleration and HR signals recorded with Rooti Rx have
620 demonstrated substantial discrimination ability in detecting moderate to severe
621 obstructive sleep apnea⁶³.

622 The Rooti Rx is used in the *LOOKING GLASS DR* satellite pilot trial to monitor HR during
623 daytime activity and nighttime sleep in hospitalized geriatric inpatients with a history of
624 falls.

625

15. Euleria Health Lab

626 Euleria Lab is a digital health platform certified as Class IIa medical software, designed
627 to deliver personalised tele-rehabilitation interventions. It integrates wearable devices
628 and biofeedback technology to monitor rehabilitation progress and detect changes in
629 motor function over time. The system includes a set of wearable inertial sensors used
630 to track movement during rehabilitation exercises⁶⁴. Two sensors are typically

631 positioned on the feet to compute spatio-temporal gait parameters across five
632 predefined motor tasks, with the aim of profiling patients in terms of balance and
633 mobility, and assessing their risk of falls. The collected data are compared against
634 normative reference values to support clinical decision making. In addition, the system
635 incorporates Bluetooth-enabled dynamometers for muscle strength assessment across
636 various body regions, and sensorised platforms for evaluating balance under both static
637 and dynamic conditions. Euleria Lab has demonstrated high validity when benchmarked
638 against a gold-standard optoelectronic motion capture system across a broad set of full-
639 body movement tasks⁶⁵.

640 Euleria Health is employed in the *MAMBO* pilot trial to identify potential digital
641 biomarkers of postural alterations in orthopedic patients.

642 *16. Noraxon Ultium Motion*

643 The Ultium Motion system (Noraxon) is a portable inertial motion capture platform
644 designed to deliver high-resolution kinematic measurements across a wide range of
645 motor tasks, including gait analysis⁶⁶ and performance assessment in high-velocity and
646 high-impact conditions⁶⁷. It utilizes a set of water-resistant, body-worn inertial sensors
647 that include high-resolution tri-axial accelerometers (± 200 g, sampling rate = 400 Hz),
648 gyroscopes (± 7000 deg/s, sampling rate = 400 Hz), and magnetometers (± 16 Gauss,
649 sampling rate = 100 Hz). Sensors can be securely affixed to the body using elastic
650 straps. Each sensor is equipped with internal memory (250 MB), allowing up to 16 hours
651 of data storage, and a rechargeable battery supporting over 8 hours of continuous
652 operation. A calibration adjustment tool is provided to refine static calibration by
653 capturing individual posture profiles and applying them to the reconstructed skeletal
654 model, thereby improving motion capture accuracy. Data acquisition and analysis are
655 performed using the myoRESEARCH software platform, which enables synchronized
656 collection of raw and processed biomechanical parameters, including anatomical joint
657 angles, joint trajectories, orientation angles, linear acceleration, and quaternions. . The
658 platform also supports seamless integration with electromyography (EMG), force and
659 pressure sensors, and *third-party* devices, facilitating high-fidelity multimodal data
660 collection.

661 In the framework of DARE, the Ultium Motion system is used in conjunction with the
662 Euleria Lab platform within the *MAMBO* pilot study.

663 *17. Dexcom G7*

664 The Dexcom G7 is a commercial, water-resistant continuous glucose monitoring (CGM)
665 system designed to provide real-time glucose tracking for individuals with diabete⁶⁸. It
666 consists of an integrated sensor-transmitter unit that utilizes advanced sensing
667 technology to deliver glucose readings with clinical-grade accuracy at 5-minute intervals
668 ⁶⁹. Compared to its predecessor (Dexcom G6), the G7 features a shorter warm-up time
669 and extended wear duration, ensuring consistent performance during daily activities,
670 including exercise and swimming. To use the Dexcom G7, users must create a personal
671 account and log into the secure Dexcom Clarity portal. The device connects via
672 Bluetooth to a compatible smartphone or a dedicated receiver, allowing for real-time
673 synchronization and access to current glucose levels, trend information, and
674 personalized alerts through the Dexcom mobile app. All collected data are stored in the
675 Dexcom Clarity cloud platform, where users can review historical trends to support
676 ongoing diabetes management. Dexcom also offers optional integration through its
677 Developer Program, which provides access to APIs for connecting glucose data with

678 *third-party* platforms and applications, thereby enabling a more comprehensive digital
679 approach to diabetes care.

680 The Dexcom G7 is employed in the *TWIN* pilot trial as a primary data source to support
681 the optimization of insulin therapy in pediatric participants with Type 1 diabetes
682 managed via multiple daily injections.

683 *18. Sleep profiler*

684 The Sleep Profiler (Advanced Brain Monitoring, USA) is a medical-grade device designed
685 for the monitoring of sleep patterns and the diagnosis of sleep disorders, such as sleep
686 apnea. It enables configurable acquisition of electrophysiological, acoustic, and
687 accelerometric signals, with adjustable sampling rates and gain settings to suit specific
688 study requirements. The device includes three frontopolar channels that capture
689 electroencephalographic (EEG), electrooculographic (EOG), and photoplethysmographic
690 (PPG) signals. An optional dual-lead cable enables additional acquisition of
691 electrocardiographic (ECG) and/or electromyographic (EMG) signals. The device is also
692 equipped with an acoustic microphone for snoring and environmental noise evaluation,
693 and a tri-axial accelerometer for movement and body posture detection. These multi-
694 modal measurements allow for the characterization of several key sleep metrics,
695 including sleep architecture and stages, sleep latency, continuity, efficiency, sleeping
696 position, snoring, and pulse rate. The Sleep Profiler operates as a standalone unit,
697 without the need for smartphone connectivity, and supports offline data transfer for
698 subsequent clinical or research analysis. The Sleep Profiler has been used in multiple
699 research studies to assess sleep quality, demonstrating high comparability with gold-
700 standard polysomnography^{70,71}.

701 *Table 2. Summary of wearable devices used across DARE pilot studies and their technical specifications. The table reports each*
 702 *device's integrated sensors, data access modality, availability of raw and processed data, software license requirements, and*
 703 *the need for a companion smartphone application for operation..*

Wearable device	Integrated sensors	Data access	Raw data available	Processed data available	Software license needed	Smartphone needed (app - iOS/Android)
ActiveInsight Geneactiv	Accelerometer Ambient light Skin temperature	It can be used as a data logger (Internet connection not required). <i>Raw</i> and processed data can be downloaded through its software (internet connection not needed), where it is also resampled to the nominal sampling frequency (100 Hz). Processed data are also available with licensed software and data transfer to the vendor's cloud.	Accelerometer Ambient light Skin temperature	Steps, cadence, stride intervals, sleep duration and efficacy, naps per day, rest-activity cycles, mid-sleep time, inter-day stability, METs, activity intensity, tremor intensity*	No	No
McRoberts Dynaport 7	Accelerometer Barometer Gyroscope Skin temperature	It can be used as a data logger (no connection required). <i>Raw</i> data can be downloaded directly to a PC using a USB cable. <i>Raw</i> data can also be uploaded to McRoberts' cloud (optional). Processed data are available using the Analytic Pipeline.	Accelerometer Barometer Gyroscope Skin temperature	Steps*, movement duration/frequency/intensity, night's rest detection, sleep posture, sleep movement time, sleep transition, BMR, DIT, AEE, TEE, PAR, PAL	Yes	No
Axivity AX6	Accelerometer Ambient light Gyroscope Temperature	It can be used as a data logger (Internet connection not required). <i>Raw data</i> can be downloaded directly to a PC using the open-source software (AX3 GUI). Processed data are available using the Analytic Pipeline provided by McRoberts (license and cloud data transfer needed).	Accelerometer Gyroscope Light Exposure Skin temperature	**	No	No
Empatica EmbracePlus	Accelerometer Gyroscope EDA PPG Temperature	<i>Raw</i> data is collected through its mobile app and must be uploaded to the vendor's cloud (GDPR Compliant, based in the USA). <i>Raw</i> and processed data can be accessed using free cloud storage and Cyberduck software to download the data via File Transfer Protocol (FTP).	Accelerometer EDA PPG Skin temperature	Heart rate, Heart rate variability, Activity intensity, Body position, Wearing detection, Energy expenditure, Step count, Respiratory rate, Activity classification, Sleep detection, MET	Yes	Yes, for real-life monitoring longer than 36 hours. (Empatica Care - iOS/Android)
Garmin Fenix 7S	Accelerometer Barometer Compass GPS Gyroscope PPG Skin temperature	<i>Raw</i> data from the accelerometer can be downloaded using an open-source app (RawLogger) that uploads a .fit file to the personal profile. Processed data can be downloaded using the Garmin Connect portal via proper APIs.	Accelerometer#	HR, HRV, respiration rate, body battery (energy levels), stress level, sleep detection and naps, steps, floors, calories, intensity minutes, active minutes, SpO ₂ (manual mode), wearing detection, activity info, training status	No	Yes. (Garmin Connect - iOS/Android).

Garmin Forerunner 255	Accelerometer Barometer GPS Gyroscope Magnetometer PPG Skin temperature	<i>Raw</i> data from the accelerometer can be downloaded using an open-source app (RawLogger) that uploads a .fit file to the personal profile. Processed data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications using a set of public Device and Web APIs.	Accelerometer#	HR, HRV, respiration rate, body battery (energy levels), stress level, sleep detection and naps, steps, floors, calories, intensity minutes, active minutes, SpO ₂ (manual mode), activity info, training status	No	Yes. (Garmin Connect - iOS/Android).
Garmin Instinct 2 Solar	Accelerometer Barometer GPS Gyroscope Magnetometer PPG Skin temperature	<i>Raw</i> data from the accelerometer can be downloaded using an open-source app (RawLogger) that uploads a .fit file to the personal profile. Processed data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications using a set of public Device and Web APIs.	Accelerometer#	HR, HRV, respiration rate, body battery (energy levels), stress level, sleep detection and naps, steps, floors, calories, intensity minutes, active minutes, SpO ₂ (manual mode), activity info, training status	No	Yes. (Garmin Connect - iOS/Android).
Garmin Vivoactive 5	Ambient Light Accelerometer PPG	<i>Raw</i> data from the accelerometer can be downloaded using an open-source app (RawLogger) that uploads the .fit file to the personal profile. Processed data can be downloaded using the Garmin Connect portal via proper APIs.	Accelerometer#	HR, respiration rate, body battery, stress level, sleep detection and naps, steps, calories, intensity minutes, active minutes, SpO ₂ (manual mode), wearing detection, activity info, training status	No	Yes. (Garmin Connect - iOS/Android).
Fitbit Sense 2	Ambient light Accelerometer PPG Skin temperature	<i>Raw</i> and processed data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications using a set of public Device and Web APIs.	Accelerometer# Light exposure# PPG# Skin temperature#	Movement (per minute), HR (1 Hz during training sessions, 1 sample every 5 sec otherwise), HRV, breathing rate, SpO ₂ , steps, sleep	No	Yes. (Fitbit app - iOS/Android)
Fitbit Inspire 3	Ambient light Accelerometer PPG	<i>Raw</i> and processed data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications using a set of public Device and Web APIs.	Accelerometer# Light exposure# PPG#	HR, step counts, exercise sessions (both logged by the user and automatically detected), calories, distance, sleep (with phases), skin temperature variations, HRV, respiratory rate, resting HR, SpO ₂	No	Yes. (Fitbit app - iOS/Android)
Polar Ignite 3	Accelerometer Ambient light Skin temperature	<i>Raw</i> data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications via SDK. Processed data can be accessed through the Polar Flow app and website.	Accelerometer#	METs, PP interval (corresponding to HR) in the QRS cardiac wave, altitude	No	Yes. (Polar flow app - iOS/Android)
Polar Verity Sense	Accelerometer Gyroscope Magnetometer PPG	<i>Raw</i> data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications via SDK. Processed data can be accessed through the Polar Flow app and website.	Accelerometer# Gyroscope# Magnetometer# PPG#	MET, PP interval	No	Yes. (Polar flow App - iOS/Android)
Polar H10	Accelerometer ECG	<i>Raw</i> data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications via SDK. Processed data can be accessed through the Polar Flow app and website.	Accelerometer# ECG#	RR interval	No	Yes. (Polar flow app - iOS/Android)
Rooti Rx	Accelerometer ECG	An Internet connection is required only to start and terminate recordings. <i>Raw</i> data must be uploaded to the Cloud (GDPR-compliant, based in	Accelerometer ECG	Activity level, activity classification, RR intervals, HRV, standard deviation normal to normal (SDNN), power spectrum, Low frequency/High	Yes	Yes (Rooti Rx app - iOS)

		Ireland) before they can be downloaded locally.		frequency (LF/HF), respiratory rate during sleep, sleep posture, sleep stage, obstructive sleep apnea events		
Euleria	Accelerometer Gyroscope Magnetometer	<i>Raw</i> data can be accessed upon request to the Euleria company.	Accelerometer# Gyroscope# Magnetometer#	Joint angles, range of motion, antero-posterior and mid-lateral load distribution, spatiotemporal gait parameters*	Yes	No
Ultium Motion	Accelerometer Gyroscope Magnetometer	<i>Raw</i> data can be accessed using the myoRESEARCH software platform.	Accelerometer Gyroscope Magnetometer	Joint angles, orientation angles, linear acceleration, joint trajectories, quaternions, spatiotemporal gait parameters*	Yes	No
Dexcom	Glucose Sensor	No access to <i>raw</i> current data. <i>Processed</i> data can be accessed by developing <i>ad-hoc</i> applications using a set of public Web APIs.	-	Glucose concentration and time derivative (1 sample every 5 minutes)	Yes	Yes
Sleep Profiler	Accelerometer, EEG, EMG, EOG, ECG, PPG, microphone	<i>Raw</i> and processed data can be downloaded using the proprietary software	Accelerometer, EEG, EMG, EOG, ECG, PPG, acoustic	Time ranges, sleep position, sleep efficiency, sleep architecture, sleep latency, sleep continuity, snoring, pulse rate	Yes	No

*Legend: MET - AEE - Activity-related Energy Expenditure; API - Application Programming Interface; BMR - Basal Metabolic Rate; DIT - Diet-Induced Thermogenesis; ECG - Electrocardiogram; EEG - Electroencephalogram; EMG - Electromyogram; EOG - Electrooculography; HR - Heart Rate; HRV - Heart Rate Variability; MET - Metabolic Equivalent of Task; PAL - Physical Activity Level; AR - Physical Activity Ratio; PP - pulse-to-pulse; PPG - Photoplethysmogram; SDK - Software Development Kit; SpO₂ - Blood Oxygen; TEE - Total Energy Expenditure; * Additional digital outcomes can be extracted using the software; ** Additional digital outcomes can be extracted using the Mobilise-D pipeline integrated in the McRoberts software license; # Raw data can be accessed upon additional steps*

704 **Web and Mobile Applications for Sensor Data Collection developed in**
705 **DARE**

706 Dedicated Web and mobile applications have been developed within the DARE initiative
707 to support wearable data collection and management, offering *user-friendly* platforms
708 that facilitate the handling of wearable data across multiple pilot studies.

709 ***UBEP Wearables Dashboard***

710 The UBEP Wearables Dashboard is a customizable data management platform
711 developed by the Unit of Biostatistics, Epidemiology, and Public Health (UBEP) at the
712 Department of Cardiac, Thoracic, Vascular Sciences and Public Health (DCTV),
713 University of Padua, in collaboration with *Sinotropy.ai* (Milan, Italy). Designed to support
714 the deployment and monitoring of wearable devices in diverse research settings, the
715 dashboard enables the seamless reassignment of devices across multiple studies and
716 is device-agnostic, allowing integration, analysis, and visualization of both *raw* and
717 aggregated data from a variety of sensor systems. The platform operates through API-
718 based interactions, either by directly querying Web APIs or by using an intermediate
719 server to communicate with low-level device-specific APIs. The interface supports real-
720 time data synchronization and offers customizable analytics pipelines, enabling flexible,
721 scalable, and reproducible data-driven assessments for heterogeneous study designs
722 (**Figure 4**).

723 Within the DARE framework, the UBEP Wearable Dashboard is used in two pilot studies
724 (*Fitmate* and *DARE-ADPKD*) to retrieve and analyze data from the Fitbit Sense 2,
725 focusing on wrist-based detection of food intake in healthy adults and individuals with
726 ADPKD, respectively.

Figure 4. Example view from the UBEP Wearables Dashboard interface, displaying time-series data retrieved from a Fitbit Sense 2 device. The interface enables researchers to visualize and download physiological parameters such as heart rate (red), blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂, blue), and sleep stages (black) over time. The panel allows for device-specific data retrieval within user-defined time windows and supports interactive exploration of individual participant records.

727 UNIPR DARE Data Collection System

728 As part of the *Garmin feasibility* pilot study conducted at the University of Parma
729 (UNIPR), a dedicated *on-premise* web infrastructure, referred to as the UNIPR DARE Data
730 Collection System (UDACS), has been developed and deployed. The system enables
731 integration with Garmin's APIs, allowing health-related data to be forwarded each time
732 participants synchronize their smartwatches via their smartphones. To begin, each
733 participant must register and log into the UDACS web dashboard to create a personal
734 account.

735 As illustrated in **Figure 5**, the UDACS architecture (built using PHP, Javascript, and SQL)
736 requires users to explicitly authorize access to their Garmin data. This is achieved
737 through an OAuth 2.0-based authorization flow provided by the Garmin Connect
738 platform. Once access is granted, the UDACS system operates under a "pull" data
739 retrieval paradigm. UNIPR servers are notified by the Garmin system each time new
740 data (formatted as a JSON dictionary) become available following a user-initiated
741 synchronization. This event-driven architecture avoids continuous polling, thereby
742 reducing computational load and improving efficiency.

743 Authorized data are then processed offline using a MATLAB script, which extracts
744 relevant features — such as the Physical Activity Index (PAI) — via a moving window
745 approach, enabling longitudinal performance analysis and participant comparison.

746

747 *Figure 5. Overview of the UNIPR DARE Data Collection System (UDACS) workflow for Garmin*
748 *wearable data acquisition and analysis. Participants first authorize access to their Garmin*
749 *data via the OAuth 2.0-based interface (left). Once access is granted, the system receives a*
750 *notification each time new data become available (center), triggering a data "push" from the*
751 *Garmin API in JSON format (top right). The collected data include physiological and behavioral*
752 *metrics such as heart rate, step count, stress level, and activity duration. These are processed*
753 *offline using MATLAB scripts to extract derived features (e.g., Physical Activity Index, PAI), which*
754 *are then visualized for analysis (bottom left).*

755 Vega Android App

756 The Vega Android mobile application has been developed to interface with the Polar H10
757 and Polar Verity Sense devices. The app enables local streaming of *raw* data via
758 Bluetooth, including UNIX timestamps and triaxial acceleration from both devices, ECG
759 data from the H10, and PPG data from the Verity Sense. VEGA supports time-
760 synchronized acquisition of raw data from multiple Polar sensors without requiring an
761 Internet connection during data collection. Within the DARE framework, the app is used

762 in two satellite pilot studies (*LOOKING-GLASS MIAR* and *LOOKING-GLASS DR*) to record
763 heart rate and activity-related metrics from healthy participants in real-world settings.

764 **Data Pipelines for Wearable Devices**

765 To ensure the extraction of valid and reliable information from wearable devices during
766 unsupervised, real-world monitoring, validated processing pipelines have been
767 identified for use in DARE pilot studies (**Table 3**). Each pipeline is optimized for specific
768 device characteristics (e.g., integrated sensors) and placement requirements (e.g.,
769 wrist-worn vs. lower-back-mounted sensors).

770 The Mobilise-d open-access Python-based pipeline⁷² ([https://github.com/mobilise-](https://github.com/mobilise-d/mobgap)
771 [d/mobgap](https://github.com/mobilise-d/mobgap)) computes 24 digital mobility outcomes⁷³ from 7 consecutive days of real-
772 world monitoring using a single inertial measurement unit (IMU) worn on the lower back,
773 equipped with an accelerometer and gyroscope. Within DARE, this pipeline will be
774 applied in pilot studies using lower-back-worn inertial sensors, specifically the Dynaport
775 7 (worn with an elastic belt) and the Axivity sensor (affixed with medical tape).

776 GGIR⁷⁴ is an open-access R package ([https://cran.r-](https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/GGIR/vignettes/GGIR.html)
777 [project.org/web/packages/GGIR/vignettes/GGIR.html](https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/GGIR/vignettes/GGIR.html)) for processing multi-day *raw*
778 acceleration data from wrist-worn devices. It incorporates validated algorithms and has
779 been extensively used in large-scale studies, including the UK biobank, to derive
780 outcomes related to physical activity, sleep, and circadian health^{75,76}.

781 The Transitions^{77,78} and Balance⁷⁹ pipelines are designed to analyze mobility and
782 balance from real-world assessments, computing metrics related to postural transitions,
783 turning, and various balance parameters. These metrics can be aggregated on daily and
784 weekly timescales. Within DARE, these pipelines will be applied in pilot studies using
785 lower-back-worn inertial sensors.

786 Cardiac activity outcomes are extracted using state-of-the-art, open-access algorithms
787 applied to *raw* ECG and PPG data. For beat-to-beat analyses, the Neurokit algorithm⁸⁰
788 is used to detect R-peaks from ECG signals, while the MSPTD algorithm⁸¹ is used to
789 detect systolic peaks and foot points from PPG signals during sleep. Heart rate and heart
790 rate variability metrics are subsequently computed using the Neurokit2⁸² Python library.
791 Due to the high prevalence of motion artifacts in PPG during daily activities, the
792 BeliefPPG⁸³ algorithm is employed outside of sleep periods to extract HR while
793 compensating for motion artifacts.

Table 3. Summary of open-access data processing pipelines used in the DARE framework. The table lists each pipeline, its required sensor position, technical and data input requirements, application domain (e.g., mobility, balance, cardiac monitoring, sleep), and the main outcomes generated.

Pipeline	Sensor position	Requirements	Domain	Outcomes
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Mobilise-D ⁷²	Lower back	Accelerometer, Gyroscope	Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Volume: walking duration, number of steps □ Pattern: number of WB, number of WB>10 s, number of WB>30 s, number of WB>60 s, WB duration, maximum WB duration, WB duration variability □ Pace: walking speed in shorter (10-30 s) WB, walking speed in longer (>30 s) WB, maximum walking speed in WB>10s, maximum walking speed in longer (>30 s) WB, stride length in short (10-30s) WB, stride length in longer (>30 s) WB □ Rhythm: cadence in all WB, cadence in longer (>30 s) WB, maximum cadence in longer (>30 s) WB, stride duration in all WB, stride duration in longer (>30 s) WB □ Variability: walking speed variability between longer (>30 s) WB, stride length variability between longer (>30 s) WB, stride duration variability between all WB
GGIR ⁷⁴	Wrist	Accelerometer	Sleep, physical activity, circadian rhythms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Sleep: sleep onset, total sleep time, wake after sleep onset, sleep efficiency, number of awakenings □ Physical activity: non-wear time, time spent in moderate-to-vigorous activity (MVPA), time spent in light physical activity (LIPA), time spent in inactivity (IN) □ Circadian parameters: acrophase, rhythm fragmentation, intra-daily stability, inter-daily variability
Transitions ⁷⁸	Lower back	Accelerometer, Gyroscope	Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Number of postural transfers, number of turns □ Duration, peak velocity, turn angle duration, normalized jerk score, mean and RMSE of accelerometer and gyroscope signals during transitions
Balance ⁷⁹	Lower back	Accelerometer and Gyroscope	Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Time-domain: range, distance, mean frequency, path, area, ellipse area □ Frequency-domain: total power, 95% freq, spectral centroid
MSPTD ⁸¹	Chest	PPG	Heart	□ Systolic peaks, systolic feet
Neurokit ⁸²	Chest	PPG	Heart	□ R-peaks
Neurokit2 ⁸² , BeliefPPG ⁸³	Chest	PPG	Heart	□ HR, HRV

Legend: HR - Heart Rate; HRV - Heart Rate Variability; PPG - Photoplethysmography; RMSE - Root Mean Square Error; WB - Walking Bout

794
795

796 Discussion

797 The aging population and the concurrent rise in chronic disease are compelling
798 healthcare systems worldwide to adopt a paradigm shift - from a *treatment-focused*
799 model to *prevention-based* and *community-oriented* approaches - and to leverage
800 digital technologies to transform health management⁸⁴. Preventive strategies, including
801 those targeting healthy young populations, are crucial to reducing the onset of chronic
802 conditions, thereby improving quality of life and lowering healthcare costs. In this
803 context, DARE has been designed to develop and integrate novel solutions into

804 healthcare pathways, with wearable technologies representing a key enabler of
805 preventive healthcare⁸⁵.

806 Within the DARE framework, sixteen pilot studies have been designed to integrate
807 wearable devices into preventive health research, each employing a specific device
808 suited to the study's requirements. These devices vary in technical specifications (e.g.,
809 sampling frequency, battery life), integrated sensors, and medical device certification.
810 The results from these pilot studies will help identify the most appropriate technological
811 solutions to incorporate into structured preventive strategies, enhancing the overall
812 efficacy and scalability of healthcare interventions.

813 A wide range of wearable devices is available on the market⁸⁶, each with distinct
814 characteristics in terms of sensor configuration, power autonomy, and data
815 accessibility. In the DARE pilot studies, device selection was tailored to the needs of
816 each study, considering monitored parameters, raw data availability, battery life,
817 usability, and participant engagement requirements. However, trade-offs are
818 unavoidable: for example, extending battery life may require reducing sampling
819 frequency or limiting the number of integrated sensors. No single device can
820 accommodate all desired specifications; thus, selection requires balancing functionality
821 with participant acceptability.

822 Standardization has been pursued wherever possible. Among the DARE studies —
823 including community-based research, clinical trials, feasibility studies, and satellite pilot
824 projects — five (31%) use the GENEActiv sensor, five (31%) use the Dynaport 7 lower-
825 back sensor, three (19%) employ the EmbracePlus wristband, and two (13%) use the
826 Axivity AX6 lower-back sensor. This standardization supports data harmonization and
827 enables the integration of validated, open-access data processing pipelines across
828 multiple studies. The chosen pipelines — such as Mobilise-D for mobility analysis⁷², GGIR
829 for wrist-worn sleep monitoring⁷⁴, and the Transitions⁷⁸ and Balance⁷⁹ pipelines for
830 postural and balance assessment — are applied based on sensor placement and raw
831 data availability. Additional validated algorithms are used to process ECG and PPG
832 signals (e.g., MSPTD⁸¹, NeuroKit⁸², BeliefPPG⁸³), enabling robust extraction of cardiac
833 outcomes in real-world settings. This approach facilitates comparative evaluation of
834 results across research groups, study designs, and populations.

835 DARE employs both commercial smartwatches and research-grade devices, depending
836 on the specific aims and resources of each pilot. Research-grade devices (GENEActiv,
837 Dynaport 7, AX6, EmbracePlus) are optimized for measurement accuracy and *raw* data
838 access, supporting advanced post-processing in domains such as physical activity,
839 sleep, and heart rate monitoring. With the exception of the Axivity AX6, these devices
840 also hold CE medical device certification, enabling use in clinical settings. Conversely,
841 commercial smartwatches, while generally more user-friendly and aesthetically
842 appealing, often limit access to raw data. To address this limitation, DARE has developed
843 custom mobile applications to facilitate data collection and export from these devices.

844 It is important to note that medical device certification alone does not guarantee
845 compliance with privacy and legal frameworks. For example, some devices
846 automatically transmit data to proprietary cloud systems located outside the European
847 Union, which may conflict with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) unless
848 appropriate safeguards are implemented. Such considerations are critical in ethical

849 review processes. Indeed, in one DARE pilot, the ethics committee rejected the study
850 protocol due to the selected wearable device (Amazfit 5) lacking medical certification
851 and using a non-GDPR-compliant data storage system.

852 Despite their potential, wearable devices in clinical and preventive contexts face
853 limitations. Accuracy and reliability can be affected by technical constraints or improper
854 placement. Studies have evaluated the accuracy of wearable devices for metrics such
855 as step count^{87,88}, heart rate⁸⁹, and sleep staging⁹⁰, generally showing promising
856 performance⁹¹. However, data privacy and security — especially when relying on third-
857 party cloud storage^{92,93} — remain major challenges. Overcoming these barriers will
858 require continued innovation in secure, interoperable digital health solutions, alongside
859 regulatory adaptation.

860 In conclusion, this paper outlines the DARE project’s strategy for wearable device
861 selection and integration, balancing study-specific requirements with the need for data
862 harmonization across pilot studies. By combining diverse wearable technologies with
863 validated, open-access data processing pipelines, DARE aims to produce high-quality,
864 comparable, and reproducible datasets to support preventive health interventions.
865 Although challenges remain—such as ensuring raw data access, optimizing battery life,
866 and meeting regulatory requirements—the integration of wearable devices into
867 preventive healthcare offers a transformative opportunity to address the growing
868 burden of aging and non-communicable diseases at scale.

Competing interests

LC is the president of DARE Foundation. SC is speaker fee from Sanofi, consultancy for Sandoz, and Novo-Nordisk. All other authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data availability

869 Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed
870 during the current study.

Authors contribution

ID, SM, LP, and LC conceptualized the manuscript. ID performed the analysis. ID, SM wrote the initial draft. ID, SM, JAS, MGB, MB, LB, LBe, JMB, EC, GC, PC, AC, BC, NC, SC, ID, GD, LD, PDF, MD, AF, GMF, MF, GF, LG, LGe, LGe, DG, AL, RL, MM, IM, VM, WM, SMe, LM, GMF, MMo, SO, FP, PP, GP, PPO, TP, GR, MS, MSi, AS, GS, GT, ET, LV, AZ, LP, LC are involved in the DARE pilot studies included in the manuscript or the DARE project management. JAS, MGB, MB, LB, GC, PC, AC, BC, NC, LD, PDF, AL, MM, IM, VM, WM, LM, SO, FP, MS, MSi, AS, GT, LV, LP, and LC reviewed the first draft and provided critical revisions. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Figures

Figure 1

Prevention areas addressed by DARE. The figure illustrates the various prevention areas investigated within the DARE initiative. Pilot studies employing wearable devices are indicated explicitly with a blue outline in their respective area(s) of focus. Note that individual pilot studies may address multiple prevention areas at a time.

Figure 2

Workflow for a wearable selection for each DARE pilot study. The workflow includes a comprehensive technical evaluation, the assessment of the ethical and practical constraints, and the harmonization of pilot studies protocols.

Figure 3

Overview of the DARE pilot studies across the life course, categorized by age group, type of prevention, setting, domain, and monitoring focus. Pilot studies are organized along three age bands: children and adolescents (<18 years), adults (18–65 years), and older adults (65+ years).

Figure 4

Figure 3: Overview of wearable devices used in the DARE initiatives, categorized by monitoring domains, attachment site, battery life, water resistance, smartphone dependency, and medical certification status. The figure lists 17 wearable devices, distinguishing between research-grade (green outline) and commercial (blue outline) products. Legend: *water-resistant, but water rating is not specified in the device documentation.

Figure 5

Figure 4. Example view from the UBEP Wearables Dashboard interface, displaying time-series data retrieved from a Fitbit Sense 2 device. The interface enables researchers to visualize and download physiological parameters such as heart rate (red), blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂, blue), and sleep stages (black) over time. The panel allows for device-specific data retrieval within user-defined time windows and supports interactive exploration of individual participant records.

Figure 6

Figure 5. Overview of the UNIPR DARE Data Collection System (UDACS) workflow for Garmin wearable data acquisition and analysis. Participants first authorize access to their Garmin data via the OAuth 2.0-based interface (left). Once access is granted, the system receives a notification each time new data become available (center), triggering a data "push" from the Garmin API in JSON format (top right). The collected data include physiological and behavioral metrics such as heart rate, step count, stress level, and activity duration. These are processed offline using MATLAB scripts to extract derived features (e.g., Physical Activity Index, PAI), which are then visualized for analysis (bottom left).